

SINGLE-CRYSTALLINE FIBRES FOR HIGH-TEMPERATURE OXIDE/OXIDE COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: A brief review of the methods of the fabrication of single crystalline oxide fibres is presented. It is shown that the internal crystallisation method (ICM) that is crystallisation of the fibres in continuous channels in an auxiliary matrix (molybdenum carcass) yields high productivity rate, which provides a base for the development of fabrication technology of oxide fibres as reinforcement for composites for very high use temperatures. The method have been used to produce a family of the fibres including sapphire, aluminium-yttrium garnet, mullite as well as some oxide eutectics. Microstructure, strength and high-temperature creep of the fibres are discussed with the emphasis on creep properties. Results of preliminary creep tests of oxide-fibre/oxide-matrix composites are also presented. It is shown that special microstructure of oxide/oxide composites yields quasi-ductile behaviour of the composites.

KEYWORDS: fibres, oxides, oxide-matrix composites, creep, fracture toughness

INTRODUCTION

Most efforts in using advance materials in machines for transportation and power generation have been always directed towards enhancing energy efficiency of the machines, which means decreasing fuel consumption per unit of useful work. Researches have done a lot to reach this goal including using structural materials with higher specific characteristics to enhance the ration of a payload to weight of the structure, improving aerodynamics, applying appropriate coatings on hot details, cooling them, etc. However, enhancing the use temperature of structural materials for hot parts of machines has been and will be always a most efficient way to reach the goal.

Most heat resistant materials for heavily loaded structural elements, those being Ni-based superalloys are approaching their physical limit set by their microstructural stability and melting points. Perhaps, this limit will be around 1100°C and a dependence of the maximum use temperature on year of the alloy development is asymptotically going to this limit. Since no other metal can be a real base for heat resistant alloys due to well-known reasons, the only alternative is to exploit ceramics. Homogeneous ceramics cannot be used in heavily loaded structures because of their inherent brittleness. Hence, non-homogeneous materials (composites) being fully or partly ceramic should be considered as future heat-resistant materials.

Crystal oxides have always attracted attention as a potential base for heat-resistant materials because of a number of the reasons:

1. They are inherently resistant to oxidation;
2. Single crystals of oxides are inherently strong;

3. They have high melting points, high elastic moduli, and low density.

Certainly, single crystals of oxides are most promising substances since polycrystalline oxides, first, are not sufficiently stable at high temperatures (say, at temperatures higher than 1200°C for alumina) and, secondly, polycrystals are known to reveal low creep resistance at high temperatures because of grain boundary sliding. Hence, single crystalline oxide fibres are wanted as a base for heat-resistant composites.

In the present paper, we present (i) a brief review of fabrication technology schemes to produce oxide fibres focusing on the internal crystallisation method (ICM), (ii) a short outline of high temperature creep characteristics of oxide single crystals, (iii) special features of some oxide fibres obtained by ICM, (iv) a procedure for evaluating creep properties of the ICM-fibres, (v) their strength and creep characteristics, (vi) some examples of ICM-fibre/oxide-matrix composites.

CRYSTALLISING OXIDE FIBRES

Certainly, the only way to produce either single crystalline oxides or those with typical eutectic microstructure is to crystallize oxide melts.

Crystallising separate fibres

LaBelle and Mlavsky [1] were the first to produce sapphire fibres by using Edge Feeding Growth (EFG) method, which can be positioned within a concept of crystallising a melt by using a shaper that was formulated by Stepanov before the WWII [2]. Stepanov introduced a shaper to pre-determine a shape and size of the capillary column at the top of which the liquid/solid interface arises. The technical adjustment of Stepanov's method to crystallising sapphire fibres was a lifting of the growth zone above the melt surface with a capillary tube in the crucible. The lower end of the tube is located near the bottom of the crucible, and the growth zone is now fixed relative to the heater independent of the level of the melt surface which goes down with time. Both a review of the corresponding techniques and discussion of the fibre growth parameters, structure and mechanical properties of sapphire fibres are presented in a paper dated by 1985 [3]. It appears that a stable growth takes place at rates no more than 0.5 - 1.0 mm/s, which makes productivity rate of the process low, so that the cost of the fibres is too high to use them in structural applications. This is despite of a certainly realised possibility to grow tens fibres in a bundle.

Japanese researchers developed μ -pulling down (μ -PD) method [4,5]; they did actually turn up down a scheme of the EFG, which simplified slightly growth procedures. Fukuda with collaborators have applied the method to produce a variety of oxide fibres [6,7,8]. They claim that the μ -PD method yields crystals with lower thermal strains compared to other growth methods and using this method makes possible to grow crystals even from incongruent melts [8]. Obviously, the method does not allow an essential decrease in the fibre cost as compared to that by LaBelle and Mlavsky.

Laser heated pedestal growth (LHPG) was used for the first time to grow single-crystal Cr-doped Al₂O₃ fibres by Burrus and Coldren [9]. Then it has been used rather intensively to grow mainly optical fibres [10], although attempts to grow structural fibres are also known [11]. There are some obvious advantages of the method: the absence of a crucible allows growing sufficiently pure crystals, a small volume of the melts increases thermal efficiency despite of a low efficiency of the laser heating and reduces mass exchange around the process zone that would be useful in growing such materials as mullite, which is characterized by a complicated phase diagram.

The methods just described have been used to produce continuous oxide fibres of high quality, which are effectively used in various non-structural applications (laser optics, scintillations, sensors, etc.). Some decades ago there were hopes to use sapphire fibres produced by EFG in structural applications so their high temperatures strength was a subject of an intensive study [12,13,14,15]. However, inherently high cost of the fibres produced by crystallisation of the melt yielded eventually a losing interest to these fibres as reinforcement in heat-resistant composites.

Crystallising a bundle of fibres – Internal crystallization method (ICM)

Internal crystallisation method was described in open literature for the first time nearly 15 years ago [16,17]. Since then a main scheme of the method as well as some variation of it has been published in a number of the papers (see for instance Refs. [18,19,20]). A schematic of the method is shown in Fig. 1. A molybdenum carcass with continuous channels in it, which is easily prepared by diffusion bonding of an assemblage of the wire and foil (step 1), is infiltrated with an oxide melt (steps 2 and 3) by the capillary force. The melt is then crystallised in the channels to form fibres in an oxide/molybdenum block (step 4). This is a main scheme of the ICM, which can be varied to attain a particular goal. For example, to ensure a homogeneous crystallographic orientation of the fibres in a block, a seed oriented in an appropriate manner [18].

Fig. 1. Schematic of the internal crystallization method.

Finally, the fibres are freed from the molybdenum carcass by dissolution of molybdenum in a mixture of acids. At the present time, the length of the fibre bundle can be up to 250 mm; a characteristic size of it is normally 50 to 300 μm . A number of the fibres with characteristic cross-sectional size of 100 μm that can be crystallised in one block by using an existing equipment can be as large as 50,000 fibres.

ICM-FIBRES

A relative simplicity of the ICM-scheme has allowed obtaining a family of single crystalline and eutectic fibres that includes Al_2O_3 (sapphire), $\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$ (YAG), $2\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\cdot\text{SiO}_2$ (mullite) $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$, $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-GdAlO}_3$. We describe here just some fibres that can serve as reinforcement for heat-resistant composites. But at first, creep characteristics of some oxides in bulk form will be presented.

Creep characteristics of some oxides

Creep characteristics of oxides, which can be of interest as materials for heat-resistant fibres, have been portrayed sufficiently well in the literature. The data published in Refs [21,22,23] were a base for temperature dependencies of stress to cause 1% of creep strain for 100 h presented in Fig. 2 for temperatures higher than 1450°C . As can be seen, many oxides, single crystals and eutectics, are characterised by sufficiently high creep resistance at high temperatures. Among the oxides tested at really high temperatures, yttrium-aluminium garnet looks preferably if nothing to say about mullite, the creep resistance of which is characterized by a single experimental point published up to now.

Fig. 2. Temperature dependence of the creep resistance (a stress to cause 1% creep strain for 100 h) of some oxides in the form of bulk crystals. Data on sapphire and garnet YAG are after Corman [21], on mullite are after Dokko et al. [22], on $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Al}_5\text{Y}_3\text{O}_{12}$ -eutectics are after Harada et al. [23].

Fig. 3. Creep resistance (stress to cause 1% creep strain for 100 h) of ICM-fibres in comparison with commercially available polycrystalline oxide fibres [29].

Fibres

Fabrication process and microstructure of both sapphire and alumina-YAG eutectic fibres have been described in detail elsewhere [16,18, 19]. All sapphire fibres were crystallized in molybdenum blocks of a customary size, that is $5\times 35\times 65\text{ mm}^3$; characteristic cross-section size of a fibre was 0.08 mm. Crystallization was conducted with a seed to ensure a homogeneous crystallographic orientation of the fibre, that is *c*-axis coinciding with the fibre axis. The rate of pulling (crystallization rate) was 70 mm/h.

Crystallization of YAG-fibres [24] was conducted by using the basic ICM-scheme presented in Fig. 1, without using the seed. An X-ray method was used to determine the crystallographic orientation of the fibres; the fibre axis occurs to coincide with the $\langle 001 \rangle$ direction.

The internal crystallisation method allows producing single crystalline mullite fibres [25,26]. Alumina-silica phase diagram [27] looks rather complicated for mullite region that makes a number of the problems while growing single crystalline mullite from the melt. In addition, values of the saturated vapour pressure of alumina and silica are too different to preserve a wanted composition of a raw mixture of the oxides in a melted state. The problems were recently solved and microstructure of the fibres was studied thoroughly. An example of the fibre microstructure is presented in Fig. 4. Fibres were crystallised either in vacuum or argon atmosphere at the pulling rate 1.75 to 5 mm/min.

Fig. 4. Cross-sections of a mullite/molybdenum block at distances of 10 mm from the block top (the left side) and of 31 mm (the right side). S, m, and g stand for sapphire, mullite, and glassy phases, respectively.

Main results of the study can be formulated as follows:

1. Mullite fibres of a composition close to $2\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{SiO}_2$ (2:1)¹ are crystallised from the melt when the composition of a raw mixture of the oxides varies from 1.8:1 to 2.1:1.
2. At the top of the oxide/molybdenum block, where crystallising starts, a multi-phased structure of a fibre is observed.
3. As the crystallisation front goes down an excess of silica in the melt is pushed out to the periphery of the fibre, mainly to the sharp corners of the fibre cross-section; sapphire phase disappears.
4. Impurities in the raw oxide mixture occur to be concentrated in a silica-rich glassy phase.
5. The fibre axis occurs to coincide with the *c*-axis of 2:1 mullite.

High temperature creep characteristics of ICM-fibres

High temperature creep characteristics of the fibres are of the primary importance; hence, we start with them. A majority of the creep tests were performed in bending of oxide-fibre/Mo-matrix specimens. With such testing two questions arise.

1. How adequate is testing fibres in molybdenum matrix?

¹ In Ref [25] there is an error in determining the mullite composition.

2. How adequate is testing in bending to evaluate tensile characteristics?

While answering the first question it should be noted that oxide melts wet molybdenum excellently and the fibres have been crystallised in the channels of the molybdenum matrix, so the fibre/matrix interface is considered to be an ideal; hence, the fibre strength is not affected by possible surface flaws. Therefore, testing fibres in their mother matrix yields their virgin properties. Any further processing of the fibres yields changes in their properties; hence, the processing should be organised in such a manner as to decrease its damaging effect on fibre characteristics. Note that the fibre characteristics are easily obtainable since a contribution of the matrix, which is fully recrystallised molybdenum, to the creep resistance of oxide/molybdenum composites even at the lowest temperature, 1000°C, is negligible, less than 10 MPa [16].

The second question obtained a positive answer in recent publications concerning creep behaviour under tension and bending of metal matrix composites [28]. An interpretation of the bending tests performed under a varying load yields approximate creep characteristics of the composite in a particular specimen. This allows excluding a number of the factors, which determine a usual scatter of the creep data of a batch of the material. In the present case, each specimen is characterised by its own set of the creep characteristics. The analysis is based on the following assumptions:

1. A composite is characterised by identical creep behaviour under tension and compression
2. The creep law of the material is

$$\dot{\varepsilon} = \eta_n \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_n} \right)^n \quad (1)$$

where η_n , σ_n , and n are constants. The value of η_n can be chosen arbitrary. In what follows, $\eta_n = 10^{-4} \text{ h}^{-1}$, which means that σ_n is the stress to cause 1% creep strain for 100 h. We call this value as creep resistance of a material on 100-hours time base.

A solution of a creep problem for a beam under bending yields a dependence of the deflection rate, \dot{f} , of the beam at its centre on applied load Q . For a beam of rectangular cross-section of height $2h$, width b :

$$\dot{f} = \eta_n \frac{1}{2^{3n+2} n^n (n+2)} \left(\frac{Q}{\sigma_n h^2} \right)^n \left(\frac{L}{b} \right)^n \left(\frac{L}{h} \right) L \quad (2)$$

in case of 3-point bending and

$$\dot{f} = \chi_n \left(\frac{M}{M_n} \right)^n \frac{L_1^2}{8} \quad (3)$$

in case of 4-point bending. Here and L is the distance between periphery supports and L_1 is the distance between the internal supports, $\chi_n = \frac{\eta_n}{h}$, $M_n = \frac{2n}{2n+1} \sigma_n b h^2$ and M is the bending moment. The solution was obtained neglecting a contribution of shear deformations to the displacement that can be essential in case of 3-point bending.

Flexure creep curves are a base for evaluating creep parameters of oxide fibres presented below, in Fig. 3. Comparing creep resistance of bulk crystals, Fig. 2, and ICM-fibres, Fig. 3, for yttrium-aluminium garnet and alumina-YAG eutectic shows an excellent correspondence

of creep resistance of these two forms of oxide specimens. This provides also an additional confirmation of the validity of the method of evaluation of creep properties of ICM-fibres by testing in bending oxide/molybdenum specimens. Note that creep resistance of Nextel 720 fibre (α - Al_2O_3 +mullite) evaluated from experimental data presented in Ref [29] is also shown in Fig. 3.

A number of important conclusions can be now drawn from the data presented; here we are to point just at three points:

1. In temperature interval from 1100 to 1600°C, values of the creep resistance of single crystalline YAG and mullite as well as that of alumina-YAG-eutectic fibres obtained by using ICM are nearly the same. YAG fibre looks slightly better than the others. Still, their creep resistance can be certainly enhanced by crystallising them in the $\langle 111 \rangle$ direction.
2. Surprisingly enough, single crystalline mullite fibres produced by ICM do not seem to be superior to, say, YAG fibres, and differs essentially from the Dokko's presented in Fig. 2.
3. Polycrystalline oxide fibres, available at the present time, obviously lose their creep resistance below a temperature of 1200°C certainly due to an intrinsic behaviour of grain boundaries.

Strength of ICM-fibres

Room temperature strength of the fibres was measured by bending a fibre over rigid cylinders of decreasing diameters and counting an average distance between fibre breaks on each step of the experiment [30]. This yields a dependence of ultimate strain on the fibre length. Provided the Young's modulus of the fibre material is known, the fibre ultimate stress is also obtained (Fig. 5). The room temperature strength of ICM-fibres are characterised by two important features:

1. The strength/scale dependence is very strong, so the Weibull exponent varies usually between 3 and 5. A reason for it is certainly an existence of sufficiently rough defects, which are located mainly on the fibre surface.
2. Coating fibres with thin layer of various materials yields healing surface defects and enhances the fibre strength.

Fig. 5. Bending strength of as-extracted and coated sapphire fibres versus fibre length. The fibres are coated by a layer of $\text{SiC}_{0.99}\text{O}_{0.01}$ of thickness 4-6 μm .

Fig. 6. High temperature strength of some oxide fibres produced by ICM. The data were obtained by testing oxide/molybdenum specimens.

These features are illustrated by experimental data presented in Fig. 5.

High temperature strength of some ICM-fibres obtained by testing oxide/molybdenum specimens in either tension or bending is illustrated in Fig. 6.

Oxide/oxide composites

An obvious problem that should be solved to make oxide/oxide composites be structural materials for very high temperatures, up to about 1600°C, is to reach an appropriate balance between creep resistance and fracture toughness (or damage tolerance). Single crystalline fibres oxide can certainly provide a high creep resistance of such composites. In fact, the first creep experiments with oxide-matrix composites reinforced with ICM-fibres do support these expectations.

It is both interesting and instructive to compare the creep resistance of a composite reinforced with ICM-sapphire fibre and that of 2D-alumina-fibre/mullite-matrix composites published recently [31]. A corresponding point for the former one is presented in Fig. 7 together with creep data for 2D-composites with polycrystalline alumina fibres in a more creep resistant matrix. A difference in the creep resistance is obvious; in terms of use temperatures it is more than 200°C due to a difference in creep behaviour of single-crystalline and polycrystalline alumina fibres.

Such kind of the ICM-fibre-based composites can be characterised by enhanced fracture toughness provided a weak fibre/matrix interface exists. The measurements of values of the critical stress intensity factor K^* for composite specimens with fibre volume fraction of 0.12 – 0.28 and the carbon interphase yield values K^* equal to $11.4 \pm 0.9 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$ as compared with corresponding values for un-reinforced matrix obtained under the same conditions being $5.9 \pm 1.1 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$ [32].

Fig. 7. Creep resistance of 1D sapphire/alumina composite at tension (specimen a00161) in comparison with tensile creep behaviour of 2D alumina/mullite composites tested by Casas and Martinez-Esnaola [31].

Fig. 8. Load versus displacement for 3-point bending of two oxide/oxide composite specimens with a special microstructure at room temperature. The specimen with lower strength is that with unidirectional reinforcement, that with higher strength is with quasi-isotropic in plane reinforcement.

At present, there is no doubt that composite fracture toughness can be greatly enhanced by organising a special composite microstructure. Preliminary experiments of such kind yield interesting load/deflection curves shown in Fig. 8. The ultimate strength of composites with

such microstructure is obviously low, but it is also obvious that optimising the microstructure will enhance the strength at the cost of reducing extremely high quasi-plasticity.

CONCLUSIONS

1. A variety of single crystalline oxide fibres have been obtained by using the internal crystallisation method.
2. The fibres retain high strength up to high temperatures. They have high creep resistance at temperatures up to about 1600°C.
3. The first experiments with oxide-fibre/oxide-matrix composites having a special microstructure reveal a quasi-ductile behaviour of them. This makes a base for building up composites with an appropriate balance between high temperature creep resistance and room temperature fracture toughness.

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